

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF MODERN PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING VOCABULARY FOR PRIMARY SCHOOL LEARNERS

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ABSTRACT

The article depicts the modern pedagogical technologies in teaching vocabulary for primary school learners, in this article the author has given the main characteristics of using pedagogical technologies in teaching vocabulary classes.

Nowadays, vocabulary is seen as a meaningful tool to be instructed and learnt in meaningful contexts (Scrivener, 1994). Despite the neglected aspect of vocabulary instruction in the past, its instruction and learning have been given much attention in the classroom in the last two decades (Douglas, 2000). Still, according to Douglas (2000), instead of giving students long list of words without any context as teachers used to do in the past, some teachers are more and more concerned about effective ways to transmit knowledge of vocabulary to students.

In addition, Carter & McCarthy (1988) state that teachers are becoming conscious of the relevance and importance of vocabulary instruction and they are conscious of their role as facilitators and guides, so teachers have given important steps to call students' attention to the importance of focus on lexical form and teachers have paid attention to successful

strategies to teach vocabulary as well. Thus, the instruction of vocabulary has come a long way in recent years and it is becoming more prevalent. Issues in vocabulary learning cannot be divorced from vocabulary instruction. So, the next step is intended to show how vocabulary acquisition is developed by learners.¹

Learning vocabulary can sound as the easiest part of the process of learning a second language. Learners just have to know new words and appropriate them as part of the language. Well that is not as easy as it may seem. How students increase their semantic knowledge can be reflected when teachers measure learner's proficiency.

A review of some findings related to my research made me analyze different authors who consider a number of vocabulary learning strategies used by second language learners. Gu and Johnson (1996), as cited by Ghazal

¹ Foundations for a unified approach to spelling and vocabulary development in the intermediate grades and beyond. *Reading Psychology*, 10, 233-253.

(n.d.) classify the vocabulary learning strategies as a) metacognitive: those where a process of selective attention and self-initiation strategies are developed; b) cognitive: includes guessing, skillful use of dictionaries and note-taking strategies; c) memory: rehearsal and encoding categories are part of this group and d) activation strategies through which new words are used in different contexts. In my opinion this classification is important to consider but teachers need to have examples of how to implement or develop these in everyday classes. For the purpose of this research some of the cognitive strategies will be considered since the students who will be part of this research are in the first year of High School and their proficiency level in English language is basic. Another author, Schmitt (1997), as cited by Ghazal (n.d.) divides the strategies into two groups: “the ones to determine the meaning of new words when encountered for the first time (determination and social strategies) and the ones to consolidate meaning when encountered again (cognitive, metacognitive, memory and social strategies)” (p. 86). One aspect that I consider as important to remark into Schmitt’s distinction is that social strategies are involved in the two groups, which make me think that interaction; group work and context are aspects to be considered in this classification. Mnemonics is an example of this strategy and it involves “relating the word with some previously learned knowledge by using some form of imagery or grouping” Schmitt (1997), as cited by Ghazal (n.d., p.86). In relation to my first research question it seems to me that Mnemonics is a strategy that can be developed for beginner students since it involves word association, classification and basic learning strategies can be developed along.

The use of modern pedagogical technologies in the educational process of the

university creates completely new opportunities for implementing the didactic principles of individualization and differentiation of teaching [5], positively influences the development of students' cognitive activity [7], their creative activity, consciousness, and realizes the conditions for the transition from learning to self-studying. It is an intensification of the learning process [12]. A number of authors, analyzing modern pedagogical technologies, came to the conclusion that modern pedagogical technologies are oriented to individualization [4], distance [2] and variability of the educational process [1, 3, 6], academic mobility of students, regardless of age and level of education [10]. There are many definitions of pedagogical technologies - a term that has become quite popular in the last decade, for example: - Pedagogical technology is a systematic method of creating, applying and defining the whole process of teaching and learning, taking into account technical and human resources and their interaction, which aims to optimize the forms of education.(UNESCO).- Pedagogical technology is a system set and order of functioning all personal, instrumental and methodological means used to achieve pedagogical goals.

- Pedagogical technology is a meaningful generalization using the definitions of all previous authors [9]. Analyzing the definitions, it is possible to allocate the criteria which are the essence of pedagogical technology: - unambiguous and clear definition of training objectives (why and for what?);

- choice and structure of content (what?);

- optimal organization of the teaching process (how?);

- methods and means of teaching (with what?);

- taking into account the necessary real level of teacher's skills (who?);

- objective methods for evaluating the results of teaching (is it so?).

Essential characteristics of pedagogical technologies are:

- diagnostic goal set and effectiveness imply guaranteed achievement of the

goals and effectiveness of the learning process;

- economy expresses the quality of pedagogical technology, providing a reserve of study time, optimizing the work of the teacher and achieving planned learning results at short intervals;

- algorithmizability, projectability, integrity and controllability reflect various

aspects of pedagogical technologies;

- correctness implies the possibility of constant operational feedback, oriented to clearly defined goals;

- visualization touches upon the application of various audiovisual and

electronic computing equipment, as well as the design and application of a variety of didactic materials and visual aids [9].

Traditional technologies are built on an explicitly illustrative method of teaching, with their use the teacher focuses on the presentation of the prepared educational material. In this case, information is almost always presented in the form of a monologue. That's why the main problems are the low level of communication skills, the inability to obtain a detailed answer from the student with his own assessment of the considered issue, the insufficient inclusion of students listening to the general discussion. Traditional pedagogical technologies have their positive

aspects: a clear organization of the learning process, systematic approach to teaching, widely used visual aids, tables, technical training aids. New living conditions put forward their demands for educating young people: they must be not only skillful, but also thinking, initiative, independent. The use of modern educational technologies in teaching practice is a necessary requirement for the intellectual, creative development of students [8, 11]. The classification of modern educational technologies is presented below:

Pedagogical technologies Achieved results
Problematic teaching Creation of problem situations in educational activity and organization of active independent activity of students to solve them, as a result we have creative mastering of knowledge, skills; the thinking abilities are developed
Multi-level teaching The teacher has the opportunity to help bad students; the students have to move faster and deeper in education. Bright students assert themselves in their abilities, the bad ones get the opportunity to experience academic success, the level of motivation for learning increases
Project methods of teaching Work on these methods makes it possible to develop the individual creative abilities of students, more consciously approach to professional and social self-determination
Research methods in teaching It allows students to independently replenish their knowledge, to deeply study the problem and to suggest ways of solving it, which is important in the formation of a worldview. This is important for determining the individual way of each student's development
Lecture Seminar Test System Allows you to concentrate the material in blocks and present it as a whole, and control is done by preliminary training of students
Technology of use in teaching play methods: role, business and other types of educational plays expansion of the horizon, the development of cognitive activity, the

formation of certain skills and skills required in practical activities, the development of general educational skills. Training in cooperation (team work, group work) Cooperation is interpreted as an idea of joint developing activities of adults and children. The essence of the individual approach is to go not from the academic discipline, but also from the student to the discipline, to go from the opportunities that the student has, to use psycho-pedagogical diagnostics of the personality Information and communication technologies. Change and unlimited

enrichment of the content of education, use of integrated courses, Internet access, whatever pedagogical technology we apply in the educational process, it is realized through the system of classes, so the teacher's task is to ensure the inclusion of each student in different activities. Educational technologies give wide opportunities for differentiation and individualization of educational activity and are aimed at the final result of the educational process - the training of highly qualified specialists.

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